

SOME ISSUES ON TEACHING VOCABULARY TO NON-PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Astanov Shavkatbek Mominjanovich

Senior teacher, department of hospital therapy
Jalal-Abad State University named after B.Osmonov

Abstract: *Teaching foreign languages, especially English, in non-philological universities, as in all educational institutions, is one of the most important tasks in training specialists in accordance with the requirements of the time. This article analyzes the role of vocabulary and exercises in developing speech skills among students of a non-philological university.*

Key words: *vocabulary, non-philological university, strategies of teaching vocabulary, learning process.*

As we know, teaching vocabulary is the base of language learning. To know a language means to master its structure and words. Thus, vocabulary in one of the aspects of the language to be taught in different institutions.

According to Hornby, vocabulary can be defined in three ways: *total number of words which make up language, range of words known to a person and translation.* Similarly, Nunan defines vocabulary in three ways: *multi-word unit, word families and core meanings.* In other words, vocabulary is the total of words and word combinations to be taught and to be learnt.

What is more important when learning a foreign language - phonetics, grammar or vocabulary? This question has been repeatedly the object of controversy between linguists and methodologists. Their opinions are still different.

They argue that the main thing is the sound design of speech, others attach special importance to its grammatical and structural design, and still others (the majority of them) recognize full priority for vocabulary.

The issues of teaching vocabulary at any level are very complex. These are the selection of lexical material for various levels of education, the selection of an active and passive vocabulary, the development of the most effective ways to introduce vocabulary, ways to consolidate and control it, a system of exercises, etc. These issues are undoubtedly relevant for a non-linguistic university.

The final selection of vocabulary for a non-linguistic university has not yet been made, neither for the course as a whole, nor for its individual stages. The lexical

minimum in universities is most often determined by the texts that students work through in the classroom and outside it.

Thematically, university vocabulary is divided into:

- 1) everyday vocabulary;
- 2) socio-political;
- 3) general scientific;
- 4) special.

In most universities in the first year in the 1st semester, household and socio-political vocabulary is studied, in the second semester - general scientific and special, in the 2nd year - special and socio-political. Active vocabulary is included in all years, but household and general scientific vocabulary is subject to special activation.

Passive vocabulary includes special vocabulary. The nature of active and passive lexical material depends on the form of its organization and purpose. In a textbook for a non-linguistic university, the following forms of lexical organization of educational material can be distinguished:

- 1) lexical exercises before the text;
- 2) text (dialogue, monologue for oral speech, monologue texts in the form of excerpts from newspapers, general scientific and special literature for reading or listening);
- 3) lexical exercises after the text.

How is the situation in a non-linguistic university? How often is vocabulary introduced? Vocabulary is acquired in the process of reading educational texts. The question of how it is more expedient to organize the assimilation of vocabulary remains unresolved. Of course, it is impossible to come up with a methodology for working on each word. But the analysis of the dictionary shows that many words have similar features and difficulties for assimilation.

Many methodologists are working on the creation of a methodological typology of the word and have already done a lot. Scientifically based methodical typology of the word helps the teacher to identify the most effective ways of introducing, reinforcing and repeating a certain type of word.

Vocabulary activation tools

Let's consider the ways of developing a lexical skill, which is a quick learning action for choosing a lexical unit, its correct combination with other units of speech and its situationality.

What means are necessary for the formation of a lexical skill? The opinion of the methodologists is unanimous - numerous exercises.

There are many lexical exercises, but you need to choose those that help you better establish a connection between vocabulary and the situation. Interesting in this

respect are the communicative exercises that develop and introduce the skills of using words in a speech situation, developed and introduced by E. I. Passov.

He identifies several stages in their organization:

- 1) perception of the word in speech;
- 2) awareness of the meaning of the word;
- 3) imitation;
- 4) designation - the ability to name an object in speech situations;
- 5) combination.

In assimilating lexical material, work is carried out simultaneously on the form, meaning and use of the word. In a non-linguistic university, lexical material is assimilated in two ways, i.e. receptively and reproductively. For this purpose, lexical exercises can be used in different stages of the lesson. Mainly lexical exercises are used before reading the text.

What is the purpose of these exercises?

By using lexical exercises before reading the text, we basically reinforce the form of the word (phonetic and grammatical), enter the meaning of the word, phrase. The meaning of the word is given taking into account the subsequent context, the types of exercises that will be used in the text are worked out. The pronunciation of new words, especially difficult ones, is practiced. Thematic vocabulary is highlighted in the exercises.

We can use lexical exercises after reading the text. These exercises are aimed at training the use of words and expanding vocabulary. A variety of work is being done with the lexical material of the text already in connection with its content, questions and answers are used, the use of a word in a new context, synonyms, antonyms, set phrases, etc.

The main work on vocabulary is carried out on the basis of the text. Vocabulary expansion occurs continuously with reading the text and using exercises that ensure the repetition of new vocabulary. When learning new vocabulary, it is important to see and hear the word, i.e. when reading. When students read the text loudly, they will develop their pronunciation skills.

Paraphrasing takes great role in expanding and consolidating new vocabulary. For example, to compose a dialogue from a monologue and to retell a text that is complex in form in your own words.

What is important for a student when working on a vocabulary?

I. For receptive language proficiency, it is important:

- 1) see, find a new word, determine the original form, find the meaning, select the desired meaning from the vocabulary column;

- 2) determine the meaning of the word by word-formation features, without looking into the dictionary;
- 3) memorize grammatical forms of the words, especially exceptions to the rules, recognize them in the text;
- 4) memorize the most common verbs and be able to recognize them;
- 5) know all auxiliary words, especially prepositions, pronouns and conjunctions;
- 6) navigate word order in a sentence.

II. For reproductive possession it is important:

- 1) be able to use the specific meaning of a word in a speech situations;
- 2) know a certain set of words and phrases on topics;
- 3) know and be able to use grammatical structures, most common in speech, the vocabulary for them is memorized on sample sentences;
- 4) be able to put a question and answer it, using a certain thematic selection of vocabulary, questions can be for a filmstrip, text, etc.
- 5) be able to make a monologic speech on the text or on a topic, using already learned vocabulary;
- 6) be able to quickly make a reverse translation of all educational texts.

We hope that the above mentioned exercises will be helpful in teaching vocabulary to the students of non-philological universities.

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